

Assessing the performance of AI-assisted mapping of building footprints for OSM

Anna Zanchetta^{1,*}, Kshitij Sharma² and Omran Najjar²

¹ Alan Turing Institute, London, United Kingdom; azanchetta@turing.ac.uk

² Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team; kshitij.sharma@hotosm.org, omran.najjar@hotosm.org

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

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Building footprints features are useful in a wide range of applications such as disaster assessment, urban planning, and environmental monitoring [1-3], and their identification has been gaining increasing interest and attention from the machine learning (ML) research in Earth Observation [4]. In the context of disaster response, accurate and prompt availability of such information is crucial [5-7]. Open source datasets of AI-generated building footprints exist (e.g. Microsoft's global buildings dataset, available through Rapid, and Google's Open Buildings for Africa and the Global South at large); however, the ML models underlying these datasets are not currently open sourced [8].

fAIr, a fully open AI-assisted mapping service to generate semi-automated building footprints features developed by the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) [9], addresses this need. fAIr stands for "Free and open source AI for Responsible mapping, that is resilient to local contexts and relates to local communities", reflecting the objective of HOT to improve and assist mapping for humanitarian aid and disaster relief. In particular, fAIr performs semantic segmentation to detect building footprints from imagery at high resolution (cm) openly available through OpenAerialMap (OAM) [10]. OAM is an open service that provides search and access to openly licensed satellite and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery uploaded by users to its website.

While in OSM building footprints mapping is currently supported in most countries through Rapid, the need remains for adjustments and corrections [11]. fAIr addresses this issue by reintroducing the *human in the loop*. In its current state, fAIr allows OSM mappers to create their own local training dataset, train/fine-tune a pre-trained Eff-UNet model, and then map into OSM with the assistance of their own local model.

In its initial release [8], the performance of the model following training was not assessed; the objective of this research is to address this gap. This paper describes the research developed to assess how the ML fine-tuning process performs, investigating the currently used accuracy metric, and comparing against different sets of evaluation metrics. This falls within the broader spectrum of research on understanding the fine-tuning process for geographic domain adaptation in image analysis validation [12,13]. The ultimate aim of this research is to advise on the performance of fAIr, by assessing the current validation accuracy and comparing against other accuracy metrics for building footprints segmentation tasks.

To test fAIr's performance, we selected twenty five urban regions from OAM imagery, seeking to represent different grades of urban characteristics from different regions of the world. The urban regions were categorised by three variables through visual inspection: *urbanity*, meaning the degree of urbanity per each region, with classes: 'rural', 'peri-urban', 'urban', 'refugee camp'; *urban density*, with classes: 'sparse', 'dense', 'grid' (a class in between sparse and dense, which shows a regular gridded or repeated spatial pattern); *roof cover type*, with classes: 'shingles', 'metal' (usually tin), 'cement', 'mixed' (a mix of the above, or other types). We then performed manual labelling on selected areas of interest (Aoi), leveraging OSM data when this was available and aligned, or else generating new OSM data while labelling the images (see fAIr-dev website [14] for a detailed explanation on the labelling process). The pre-processing of the Aoi images, to generate one training dataset per urban region, was performed through fAIr-dev website [14] and produced 256x256 georeferenced tiles for both the original RGB images (ground truth) and OSM data (the labels), where the latest were converted to binary masks for the analysis. The number of tiles per region varies depending on the training dataset, for a total of 8400 images (about 350 per region in average) at three different zoom levels (19, 20, 21).

Having labelled the Aois, the next step was semantic segmentation. In computer vision (CV), semantic segmentation is the task of segmenting an image into semantic meaningful classes, which is performed with convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures [15]. The deep learning CNN model used in fAIr is called RAMP (Replicable AI for MicroPlanning), and its architecture originates from a typical encoder-decoder network, a computational process where images are trained on labelled data, called Eff-UNet model [16]. This consists of an EfficientNet as the encoder for feature extraction, with UNet decoder for reconstructing the segmentation map [17]. RAMP was chosen as an outcome of a series of feasibility studies and AI challenges to segmenting buildings for disaster resilience, happening between 2020 - 2022 and supported by HOT and other international bodies [8].

fAIr is trained using *categorical accuracy* (i.e. the ratio of samples that were correctly classified over all predictions made) at the pixel level as an accuracy metric, with categorical cross entropy as the loss function. Based on a literature review of the performance of metrics in image analysis validation, we chose to compare the current metric against four commonly used validation metrics [13; 18]: *precision*, also known as Positive Predictive Value (PPV), the fraction of actual positive samples among the positive predictions; *recall*, also called sensitivity or True Positive Rate (TPR), the fraction of true positive predictions over all positive samples; *F1 score*, the harmonic mean of PPV and TPR; *intersection over union* (IoU), also known as Jaccard index, a measure of the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth.

We ran the ML training on all twenty five training datasets using an Nvidia Tesla T4 GPU, at four different batch sizes (2, 4, 8 and 16), and for a number of epochs fixed to 20, to be consistent with the current functioning and suggestions of fAIr. For each urban region, the training provided a fine-tuned model backbone, and the value at each epoch of the five metrics, defined using built-in Tensorflow functions. In order to use the fine-tuned model backbones for inference later on, fAIr needs to store the model checkpoints. This is currently done using early-stopping, which means that the model is stored at the epoch at which the categorical accuracy has its maximum value for validation during training. In our analysis we consider this epoch, per each urban region, as the benchmark against which to evaluate the

model performance. In other words, when categorical accuracy is at its highest, how do other metrics perform? In particular, how about IoU, which is the suggested metric for this type of image analysis problem [13]?

In a preliminary analysis we compared the values of each metric against one another, at the epoch at which categorical accuracy was the highest for validation after training. This was done taking into account the three variables mentioned above, and it showed that the degree of urbanity and roof type do not seem to have a relevant influence on the performance, at least for the twenty five regions considered in the analysis, and were therefore discarded. When considering only the density variable, an analysis on the batch size showed that the distribution of the metrics is consistent across the batch sizes, with variations being attributable mainly to density; therefore the batch size is also discarded as a variable.

The values for all the metrics grouped by the density classes are plotted in Figure 1 for the four batch sizes (2, 4, 8 and 16), and for all the urban regions. Clearly a trend is seen going from sparse to dense urban regions, with IoU and recall performances being mostly affected. The results thus point to density being the major driver in affecting the model accuracy during validation. Among all the twenty five selected urban regions and for all the accuracy metrics, dense regions perform worse on average, 4.2% less than sparse and 4.8% less than grid regions. These figures grow respectively to 7.8% and 7.7% when considering IoU alone. While ideally both precision and recall should have high values (closer to 1), in our

Figure 1. Boxplot with values of five validation accuracy metrics (categorical accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, IoU) for each urban region (left y axis) and grouped by the density variable (right y axis), for four batch sizes (2, 4, 8, 16, bottom x axis).

case high values for precision mean that most detected objects match ground truth objects, but low recall implies that many ground truth objects have been missed, and this also affects F1 score. Low values for IoU imply that the model struggles in distinguishing objects from their backgrounds, a behavior that resonates with more densely populated areas in this case.

In conclusion, fAIr shows to have more potential for mapping buildings in sparsely populated areas than in urban centres. When using fAIr at its current state, one should be aware that building footprints segmentation in dense areas will be less performant than in gridded and sparse areas, with IoU, the recommended metric for this CV task, giving the lowest model performance. Other factors, like the roof cover type and regionality, do not seem to have a relevant effect on the model performance. Future research will concentrate on using other factors to help drive the fine-tuning process, like loss regularisation, and on how other variables, like the zoom level, can affect the performance. The analysis will also be extended to the assessment of the inference process. All the code used in the research is available at <https://github.com/ciupava/fAIr-utilities>, while the preprocessed data is downloadable directly from the fAIr-dev website [14].

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